

THE ROLE AND TASKS OF THE WORLD TRADE ORGANIZATION IN THE PROCESS OF REGULATING FOREIGN TRADE

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Annotation: In this article, the role of the WTO in the regulation of foreign trade relations of countries and the types of regulation of foreign trade and what kind of organization the World Trade Organization is, the system of legal norms in the management of international trade by the organization. About the impact of WTO tasks, requirements, agreements on foreign trade relations.

Key words: Uzbekistan, countries, tasks, rules, regulation, liberalization, World Trade Organization, foreign trade, membership, protectionism, GATT, liberalization.

Access

Currently, foreign trade is an important component of the activity and development of each individual country and the world as a whole, because no country can develop without creating an effective system of economic relations with the economy of other countries. In the context of international economic relations, national economies are considered not as separate economic systems, but as a systematic complex of interactions of economic entities in the world market, therefore, the role of foreign trade in the development of the national economy of the country increases significantly.

International trade is one of the advanced forms of building international economic relations, an important means of shaping the world economy, helping to establish relations between countries and strengthen their interdependence in the field of international exchange of goods, services and products.

In addition to the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade, the main document regulating foreign trade of WTO member states is the Trade Facilitation Agreement (TFA). This Agreement establishes the procedure for simplification, coordination, automation, in particular, formalization of procedures related to the import and export of goods, acceleration of their formalization, customs payments, detailed description of transit mechanisms for goods and issues of customs cooperation.

The World Trade Organization was established on January 1, 1995. The basis of this organization is the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT) concluded in 1947. 98% of the world's foreign trade turnover falls on WTO member countries. Currently, 164 countries are members of this organization, 22 countries are observers.

Members of the World Trade Organization - in dark green, members of the World Trade Organization and the European Union - in light green, observers - in blue¹

This organization has cooperation mechanisms and practices with the United Nations. The WTO is designed to regulate the trade and political relations of the Organization's participants based on the set of agreements of the Uruguay Round

¹ https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Jahon_savdo_tashkiloti#/media/Fayl:World_Trade_Organization_Members.svg

(1986-1994) of multilateral trade negotiations. These documents are the legal basis of modern international trade.

The WTO oversees a wider range of trade agreements than the GATT (including trade in services and trade-related intellectual property rights issues) and has far greater powers to improve decision-making and implementation by member organizations. An integral part of the WTO is a special mechanism for resolving trade disputes.

Since 1947, the multilateral trade negotiations (MTP) under the auspices of the GATT have been used to discuss the global problems of liberalization and the prospects for the development of world trade. To date, 8 rounds of the ICC have been held, including Uruguay, and the ninth is underway. The main goal of the WTO is to further liberalize world trade and ensure fair competition conditions.

The official supreme body of the organization is the WTO Ministerial Conference, which meets at least once every two years. During the existence of the WTO, eleven such conferences were held, almost every one of which was accompanied by active protests from opponents of globalization.

The organization is headed by the CEO, who is subordinated to the appropriate board. It is a special commission on trade policy of the countries subordinate to the Council, designed to monitor the implementation of their obligations under the WTO. In addition to the general executive functions, the General Council manages several other commissions established on the basis of agreements concluded within the framework of the WTO. The most important of these are the Council on Trade in Goods (called the GATT Council), the Council on Trade in Services and the Council on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights. In addition, there are many other committees and working groups subordinate to the General Council, which are aimed at providing the higher bodies of the WTO with information on developing countries, financial policy, financial and budgetary issues, etc.

The main **principles and rules** of the GATT/WTO are as follows:

- mutual provision of the most favored nation (MFN) regime in trade;
- reciprocity of national regime (NR) for goods and services produced abroad;
- regulation of trade primarily by tariff methods;
- refusal to use quantitative and other restrictions;
- transparency of trade policy;
- settlement of trade disputes through consultations and negotiations, etc.

Among the above methods of state regulation, we can distinguish tariff and non-tariff regulation. One of the most important components in the tariff regulation of foreign economic activity is the customs tariff. Customs tariff means a set of customs payment rates applied to goods transported across the customs border, systematized in accordance with the commodity nomenclature of Foreign Economic Activity of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The application of the customs tariff is based, first of all, on the rules for determining the customs value of goods and the import duty.

The use of customs fees in the context of globalization has a number of main features. The high dependence of national economies on global processes limits the state's ability to set customs duty rates and reduces the effectiveness of customs tariff measures, since most developed and developing countries are bound by contractual relations to ensure the stability of the customs tariff regime. international trade. Membership of countries in international integration bodies implies the limitation of economic sovereignty, including the refusal to collect customs fees, since most of these organizations assume the existence of a free trade area or a customs union.

In turn, the development of international trade is the result of its regulation by the World Trade Organization, the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade, or the elimination of discrimination against several countries.

One of the main goals of the World Trade Organization (WTO) is to prevent self-defense and eliminate the use of protectionism. WTO is the only international organization that governs international trade rules. The WTO is based on

agreements agreed and signed by a group of trading countries. These agreements provide a legal framework for international commerce. They are important negotiated documents that hold countries accountable for conducting their trade policies within agreed criteria. Considering that the agreements are agreed and signed by the governments of the countries, their purpose is to help the developers of goods and services and those involved in their export and import to operate successfully in the world market.

The main activities of the WTO are:

- ❖ conducting negotiations on the reduction or elimination of trade barriers (import duties and other barriers to trade) and the harmonization of international trade rules (for example, anti-dumping measures, subsidies, product standards, etc.);

- ❖ managing and monitoring the implementation of agreed WTO rules on trade in goods, trade in services and trade-related aspects of intellectual property rights;

- ❖ Monitoring and analyzing the trade policy of WTO members, as well as ensuring the transparency of regional and bilateral trade agreements;

- ❖ Resolving disputes between WTO members regarding the interpretation and application of WTO agreements;

- ❖ increase the capacity of developing countries and government officials in international trade issues;

- ❖ facilitating the membership process of countries that are not yet members of the organization;

WTO agreements cover almost the entire field of international trade policy and an important part of international commercial practice, in particular:

- regulation of customs and tariffs;
- regulation of anti-dumping and application of countervailing duties;
- use of subsidies and compensation measures;
- non-tariff restrictions;

- quantitative regulation and licensing of export and import, prohibition of export and import;
- activity of state trade enterprises;
- customs unions and free trade zones;
- requirements for customs clearance, fees, foreign trade documents;
- internal taxes, levies, regulations on internal trade;
- protection measures in trade;
- technical barriers to trade;
- sanitary and phytosanitary measures;
- rules of origin of goods;
- trade in services;
- trade aspects of protection of intellectual property rights, including trade in counterfeit goods;
- textile and clothing trade;
- trade of agricultural products;
- implementation of state purchases;
- sale of civil aircraft;
- trade aspects of investment measures;
- international trade and environmental protection.²

WTO agreements are legal documents covering a wide range of world trade issues, creating a number of conveniences in the regulation and liberalization of foreign trade. Including:

The principle of giving as much comfort as possible. According to the charter, each of the member countries applies equal conditions to all other members as trading partners. If a country gives an opportunity to another trading partner, then the same regime must be applied to other WTO member countries to ensure the operation of this principle.

² <https://www.wto.org>

Exceptions are allowed. For example, countries may conclude regional agreements that do not apply to trade in goods outside of these groups. Or, a country can block certain state goods that trade illegally. Countries may also apply exceptions to certain restrictions on the provision of services. Treaties allow for such exceptions, but subject to certain specified conditions. In general, the QBR statute prevails over the definition of WTO rules and regulations.

Trade without discrimination. The country should not discriminate between its trading partners and between domestic and foreign goods, services and persons.

Elimination of trade barriers. Gradually remove existing trade barriers through negotiations.

Predictable sales. Foreign investors, companies and governments must ensure that trade barriers (including tariffs, notary barriers, etc.) are not imposed unreasonably, and market liberalization obligations are "bound" to the WTO.

Improving competitiveness. WTO rules prevent "unfair" practices such as export subsidization and dumping.

Favorable conditions for underdeveloped countries. Provide adequate level transitions and custom modes.³

³ Jahon savdo tashkiloti va O'zbekiston o'quv qo'llanma. J.Qodirov, Z.Makkamov-2021

Structure of the Organization

The general advantages of WTO membership can be summarized as follows:

✓ Getting more favorable conditions for entering the world markets of goods and services based on the predictability and stability of the development of trade relations with the member countries of the World Trade Organization, including the transparency of their foreign economic policy;

✓ Eliminate trade discrimination by accessing the WTO dispute settlement mechanism, which ensures that national interests are protected in case of violations by partners;

✓ opportunity to implement their current and strategic trade-economic interests through effective participation in the development of new rules of international trade.

Development of international trade between the Republic and other countries of the world, optimization of the composition of the country's imports and improvement of the production of national products and an increase in its quantity are the cause of further liberalization of foreign economic activity.

Foreign trade has a direct impact on the country's economy, and its further liberalization creates a basis for the development of the national economy.

Regulation of foreign economic activity with customs fees means customs fees and their rates applied to goods, as well as preferences and benefits granted from customs fees, in order to ensure the effective structure of foreign trade, protect domestic producers from unhealthy foreign competition, and stimulate the attraction of direct investments. Currently, taking into account the reforms in the regulation of foreign trade and the global changes caused by the coronavirus pandemic, it is necessary to take into account the following principles in the processes of optimizing the application of customs fees:

- application of advanced foreign experience, international principles and norms in improving the system of regulation of foreign economic activity with customs payments;

- creation of conditions for providing local producers with raw materials and materials used in the production of export-oriented products that are not produced in the republic;
- to create facilities for the import of modern technological equipment and techniques in order to establish new productions;
- unification of rates of customs fees for goods related to the commodity nomenclature code of foreign economic activity during customs clearance;
- promotion of attracting foreign direct investments;
- unification of excise tax rates for goods subject to excise tax, applying it to goods harmful to human health and the environment.⁴

The amount of duty and tax rates has a direct impact on the development of the country's foreign trade and plays an important role in the formation of the country's budget revenues.

There are several scientific views of the world's scientists on the regulation of the economy, including foreign trade, with taxes, including: according to the famous Chinese philosopher Sun Sze: "Excessive taxation will cause various robberies, serve to enrich the enemies, and as a result, the state will fall into crisis."

According to J.M. Keynes, besides fiscal function, taxes have economic regulation, stimulation and income management functions, these functions of tax arise from the need to use it as a means of regulating the economy and ensuring sustainable economic growth.⁵

Summary

In conclusion, we should say that duties and taxes have a regulatory and incentive function. Improving their use in the regulation of foreign trade leads to effective structural changes in the economy, increases the competitiveness of the national economy, and serves to supplement the state budget revenues.

⁴ Tashqi savdo siyosatida notarif metodlarning qo'llanilishi va zamonaviy xususiyatlari, Qobiljon Abduqodirovich Isayev, TDIU tadqiqotchisi.

⁵ Jo'rayev A., Myeyliyev O., Safarov G'. Soliq nazariyasi. O'quv qo'llanma. – T.: Toshkent Moliya instituti, 2004. – 166 b.

The use of foreign trade regulation tools in the foreign trade policy of the countries participating in the international market in recent years is somewhat obvious. Instead of the liberalization of world trade, almost all countries are trying to use other types of means other than the traditionally accepted tariff and notary methods in order to protect their domestic markets or to support their exporters operating in the foreign market. However, the World Trade Organization continues its policy aimed at ensuring the free movement of goods, products, work and services, despite the contradiction of such protectionist actions and attempts.

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